

The Axiology of Related Emotions in the Phraseological Units of the Tatar Language

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Abstract: The meaning and emotional coloring of phraseology in the Tatar language may depend on the context and method of use. For example, the same phraseology may have different meanings and emotional connotations in different situations. In this study, we use a corpus provided by these researchers to analyze the expressions of emotions in the Tatar language through a systematic corpus analysis. The active components of the phrase semantic subgroup “joy and happiness” are kuk (sky), bakhet (happiness), yorak (heart), and kunel (soul). The active components of the phrase semantic subgroup “calmness and ease” are somaticisms, kunel (soul), yorak (heart), and жән (soul).

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Tatarca,
deyim birim,
duygu,
deyimsel anlam

Tatar Dilinin Deyim Birimlerinde İlgili Duyguların Aksiyolojisi

Özet: Tatar dilinde deyimlerin anlamı ve duygusal renkleri, bağlama ve kullanım amaçlarına bağlı olabilir. Örneğin, aynı deyim farklı durumlarda farklı anlamlara ve duygusal çağrışımlara sahip olabilir. Bu çalışmada, Tatar dilindeki duygu ifadelerini sistematik bir bütüncü analizi yoluyla incelemek için araştırmacılar tarafından oluşturulan bir derlemi kullanmaktayız. Bulgulara göre anlamsal alt grup olan “sevinç ve mutluluk” ifadesinin etkin bileşenleri kuk (gökyüzü), bakhet (mutluluk), yorak (kalp) ve kunel'dir (ruh). Diğer bir anlamsal alt grup olan “sakinlik ve rahatlık” ifadesinin etkin bileşenleri bedensel bileşenler olan, kunel (gönül), yorak (kalp) ve жән (ruh)'tur.

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1. Introduction

The trend toward logical analysis of language in modern linguistics has strengthened. This trend implies investigating linguistic, logical, and cultural concepts common to scientific theories and ordinary consciousness—the logical analysis of language results, among other things, in anthropocentrism in language. Robert Redfield's concept states that culture consists of those “everyday understandings manifested in acts and artefacts that characterize societies”. These understandings are prerequisites for action; therefore, those with a common culture also possess standard modes of action. Culture is not a static entity but a continuous process; norms are creatively revised daily in social interaction. Those who participate in collective interaction treat each other based on a set of expectations, and the implementation of what is expected consistently confirms and reinforces their attitudes. In this respect, people in each cultural group consistently support each other's attitudes since each person responds to the other in the expected way. In this sense, culture is a product of communication (Makena, 2023; Redfield, 2006).

While trying to understand a particular culture, linguistic elements of that particular culture must be closely analyzed (Kokorina *et al.*, 2023 a, b; Makena & Feni, 2023; Omodan & Addam, 2022; Surguladze & Kakhidze, 2019) such as a closer look at the phraseological vocabulary of the language as they help us understand how each group makes sense of the world around them. Phraseological units figuratively reflect the real existing phenomena by attaching a figurative meaning to the word (Taylor, 2022). No language would not have phraseological units. Thus, phraseological units emerge based on figurative representations of reality, reflecting a community's historical or spiritual experience (Teliya, 1996).

Phraseological units are linguistic units that emerged due to the extensive experience of the nation accumulated over many years. They summarize the centuries-old cultural development of the people (Abulhanova *et al.*, 2019; Gabidullina *et al.*, 2019; Amaechi & Motalenyan, 2023; Pogosyan, 2021 a, b). The semantics of phraseological units are first and foremost associated with a person's emotional and psychological state. The phraseological units reflect the language's emotional and expressive features and poetic specifics. In the authors' opinion, the expressive function of phraseological units plays a significant role in the formation of emotional speech and actively contributes to the expression of all kinds of emotions, preserving the character of evaluation of a certain phenomenon (Mashudi *et al.*, 2022; Minnegalieva *et al.*, 2020). They acutely and accurately convey a person's opinion and attitude toward this or that phenomenon. Most phraseological units convey information primarily through emotive-evaluative and figurative representations.

Emotionality is an indispensable human quality since every person can experience emotions. Psychologists distinguish more than 500 types of emotions. Emotions are diverse and can be conveyed in language using various linguistic means and language units (Dube *et al.*, 2023; Nureeva *et al.*, 2019; Zulham *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the human emotional system should also be studied from the perspective of linguistics. Emotions significantly affect human activity and, in most cases, determine a person's actions. Therefore, emotions have received much attention since ancient times. Emotions are among the essential factors governing human behavior. Emotions are involved in all areas of human life (spiritual, intellectual, and physical). However, the scientific study of emotions remained beyond researchers' field of view for a long time. In his works on psychology, Lange (1996) noted, “In psychology, the feeling takes the place of Cinderella, unloved, persecuted, and eternally plundered in favor of her older sisters – ‘mind’ and ‘will’”. This idea can be used as a basis in linguistics because, for a long time, the formal

understanding of emotions has dominated over the substantive one. Since the 1970s, linguists' attention has shifted from studying language structure to its functioning.

For a long time, linguistics did not address the issue of emotions. Contemporary linguists offer many different theories dealing with the origin and essence of emotions. Nevertheless, there is no clear definition revealing the content of emotions. Each researcher explains emotions from his or her own perspective. Modern linguistics takes into account the importance of a person's emotional sphere (Aubakirova *et al.*, 2024; Masekela *et al.*, 2024; Nurjain *et al.*, 2023; Wu & Turner, 2023; Zorzos & Avgerinos, 2022). Different authors study different aspects of emotions (for example, evolutionary and molecular biology, physiology, neurophysiology, psychology, cybernetics, philosophy, psychology, sociolinguistics, general linguistics, and stylistics). Thus, scientists in different planes of different branches of science are trying to create a fundamental theory of emotions. It is crucial to study how emotions are expressed in language.

2. Methods

The expression of emotions in the Tatar language is underexplored, although this issue has been discussed in studies such as Beshirova (2010), Galiullina and Galieva (2014), and Safiullina (2001), *Tatar leksikologiyase* (2015). Recently, the first volume of the three-volume edition *Tatar leksikologiyase* was published (Krylova *et al.*, 2020). Works by Vakhitova (2013), Gabbasova (2002) and Galieva (2016), among others, are also noteworthy as they contain various examples of expressions of emotions in the Tatar language. In this study, we use a corpus provided by these researchers to analyze the expressions of emotions in the Tatar language through a systematic corpus analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

Emotions can be divided into positive and negative. For instance, Arsent'eva and Arsent'eva (2017) developed a scale encompassing ten emotions: affection, joke, irony, humiliation, accusation, insult, rudeness, etc. Each emotion associates its emergence with how the subject relates to an object or person (Arsent'eva & Arsent'eva, 2017; Husnutdinov, 2015). Izard (1977) also distinguishes ten basic emotions: interest, joy, surprise, suffering, hatred, disgust, humiliation, fear, accusation, and shame. He believes these emotions constitute the semantic center of emotive vocabulary (Husnutdinov *et al.*, 2022). A person, perceiving the surrounding processes and phenomena, highlights only those events that are important to him or her. It is this process that is reflected in emotions. Cowie *et al.* (2001) state that only certain types of idioms express emotional states. They divide these idioms into three groups:

1. Idioms express a person's hatred. These types of idioms are seen as taboo since they often use components of religious themes and somatisms. This group includes curses and expressions with the meaning of contempt.
2. Idioms express a person's condescending attitude toward others. Language units with the meaning of disdain are understood to be units expressing a depreciative attitude.
3. Idioms express a person's slightly ironic or humorous attitude toward an object or a person (Nureeva *et al.*, 2019; Sibgaeva & Huseynova, 2022).

In the 17th century, French scientist Descartes identified six basic human feelings: surprise, love, hatred, desire, joy, and suffering. Likewise, Simonov (1986) distinguishes four pairs of basic emotions: pleasure–hatred, joy–sadness, trust–fear, triumph–anger. Besides, the psychologist also identifies secondary emotions: excitement and interest. Bain (1970), one of

the main representatives of associative psychology, states that there are 12 different human emotions. The famous German physiologist and psychologist It can also be stated that human emotions have more than five thousand meanings, but due to the lack of words, not all of them can be expressed with the help of lexical units (Sibgaeva *et al.*, 2018).

The analysis of many groups of emotions made it possible to conclude that one phraseosemantic subgroup can include phraseological units expressing several related emotions of different degrees of intensity (for example, “phraseosemantic subgroup of surprise”; “phraseosemantic subgroup of grief, suffering, sadness, despondency”, etc.). All these phraseosemantic subgroups are united under positive, negative, and neutral emotions. Thus, a person’s state can be considered in five aspects: physical, emotional, state of mental activity, mental-psychic, and emotional-physical conditions. This study analysed the semantics of phraseological units expressing a person’s state and the structure of relations within the phraseosemantic subgroup “joy, happiness” regarding a person’s emotional state.

Joy generates an elevated mood; happiness arouses a feeling of joy and complete satisfaction with life. Joy and happiness are closely related to each other. However, there is a difference between these two feelings: happiness is a personal feeling that can be joyful for another person, but this joy cannot make the other person happy. Happiness is related to a person’s inner harmony and is a deep feeling. Joy is the emotion caused by well-being, success, or good luck and is usually associated with intense, continuous happiness.

In the Tatar language, the state of joy and happiness is very often accompanied by laughter: *эче катып кәлү* – *eche katıy kelü*; *шатлыктан (тәгәри-тәгәри) тәгәрәп кәлү* – *shatlyktan tægärär kelü*; *шатлыгыннан авызын жңыеп ала алмый* – *shatlygynnan avyzyñ jñyep ala almyj*; *кәлә-кәлә эч кату* (*катуга сабышу*) – *kelä-kelä eç katır*; *егылыт кәлү* – *egylıt kelü*; *егыла-егыла кәлү* – *egyla-egyla kelü*; *авызы колакка (колагына) жңиткән* – *avyzy kolakka jñitkän*; *авызы колакта* – *avyzy kolakta*.

From the Bakhtinian perspective, there are three ancient sources of laughter:

1. Hippocratic philosophy of laughter – therapeutic;
2. Aristotle’s formula: “Of all living beings, only man is endowed with laughter”;
3. the image of laughing Menippus in the afterworld, Lucian emphasizes the association of laughter with death (as cited in Arsent’eva & Arsent’eva, 2017).

In the Tatar language, there are phraseological units with national specificity used to express the feeling of joy: *кош тоткандай булу* – *kosh totkandaj bulı*; *бәхет кошы* – *bähet koshy*; *бәхет кошы тоткан күк булу* – *bähet koshy totkan күк bulı*; *алтын кош тоткан кебек* – *altyn kosh totkan kebek*.

The bird of happiness, the phoenix bird, the firebird, the kingbird – this is the bird Semrug (Сәмруг). In Iranian mythology, Simurgh is a mythical creature, the king of all birds. It is also known in the mythology of Turkic-speaking peoples in Central Asia and the Volga region. Persians and Uzbeks called it Simurgh, Kazakhs – Samuryk, and Tatars – Semrug. The legend states that this bird lived atop the highest mountain. The mountain was so high that no one could reach its summit on foot or horseback, no matter how long they climbed. No one was allowed to see Semrug – neither beast, nor bird, nor man. It was only known that its plumage was more beautiful than all sunrises and sunsets on Earth put together. Semrug was brilliantly beautiful, and its wisdom was as boundless as the ocean. Only those people who got up very early and worked until late at night could see this bird and attain happiness.

The image used in the phraseological unit “Golden Bird”, addressed to a joyful person, is borrowed from a fairy tale. The hero, having gone through hard trials, managed to catch the golden bird symbolizing happiness. *Атка менгәндәй булу – Atka mengändaj bulu; ат алгандай шатлану – at algandaj shatlanu.* For the Tatar people, a horse was a support and helper in the household. In the phraseosemantic subgroup “Шатлык – Shatlyk, бәхет – bəhet”, phraseological units with the component “ат – at” are actively used. Horses satisfied almost all the needs of the Tatar people. For a long time, the Tatars led a nomadic life; there was no need to prepare horse fodder for winter or to build stables. The horse skin was used for making clothes and utensils, and the meat was used for food. There was also a separate breed of Tatar horses – short, strong, fast, and undemanding. It should be noted that in ancient Turkic languages, the word *канатлану – kanatlanu* had a figurative meaning “ат алу” (“take a horse”), “атлы булу” (“have a horse”). Indeed, when a person feels joy, he or she feels inspired: *канатлы – kanatly; жәйдак – jəjdak; канат жәю – kanat jəju; канатланып китү – kanatlanyp kitü.*

The following phraseosemantic subgroup includes a large number of phraseological units formed using the cosmonym *күк* (“sky”). In the epoch of tribal fragmentation, people believed that the Supreme Power (Tanrı), symbolizing the sky and deciding the fates of peoples and countries, resides in the seventh heaven (Husnutdinov *et al.*, 2016). There is a belief that *катка, капус* (“dome”) opens once a year, and the person who sees it becomes happy. It was believed that when God opens *капус*, he hears people’s wishes and fulfills them: *күк капусы ачылу – күк карису ачули; күк кабагы (капусы) ачылган көн – күк kabagy achyлган көн.* One more group formed using the component *күк* (“sky”): *жиде кат күккә менү – жиде kat күккә менү; жиденче кат күккә ашу – жиденче kat күккә ashu; түбәсе күккә тию – түбәсе күккә tiyu.* Allah created the sky with seven levels. Hell is in the underground, and paradise is in heaven, it has seven levels; reaching the seventh level is bliss and goodness.

From ancient times, speaking about some happy person, the Tatars used phraseological expressions: *бәхет йөзлеге белән туу* (“to be born in a shirt”), *бәхет йөзеге белән туу* (“to be born with a lucky ring”). The etymology of the phraseological unit *бәхет йөзеге белән туу- bəhet jəzege belən tuu* is connected with the prophet Suleiman. He ruled not only over all kings in the world but also over birds, insects, animals, winds, demons, etc. He gained such boundless power with the help of his magic ring. Not only he, but also the owner of this ring was supposed to be happy.

In phraseological units conveying the feeling of joy, somatisms are often used: *авыз колакка житү – авуз kolakka jitiü; авыз еру; йөз яктыру – авуз ери; јез yaktyru/ ачылу; эч катып көлү; аяк жиргә тимәү (аяк жиргә тияр-тимәс) – ачули; еч katyp көлү; аяк zhirga timäü.* The components *йөрәк* (“heart”) and *күңел* (“soul”) are directly associated with the world of human feelings and are actively used to form phraseological units in the phraseosemantic subgroup “Joy, happiness”: *күңел күтәрелү – күңел күtarelü; күңел кинәнү – күңел kinänü; күңел кузгалу – күңел kuzgalu; күңел көрәю – күңел көräju; йөрәк жилкенү – jəräk zbilkenü,* etc.

3.1. Phraseosemantic Subgroup “Calmness, Ease”

Calmness is a state of peace and satisfaction with suppressing fear, anxiety, unrest, irritation, and other negative emotions. Ease means eliminating difficulties, pleasure, and an elevated state of mind. Unhappy people express an excellent mood as calmness and relief, a feeling of satisfaction in relations with the world and people (Sibgaeva *et al.*, 2018). The specific linguocultureme forms the following phraseological units: *кул белән сытырып – kul belən syryryp / сыйтан алгандай булу – syrtap algandaj bulu; тел белән ялман алгандай булу – tel belən yalmap algandaj bulu,* etc. In the past,

prayers and incantations were used to treat the evil eye, various ailments and pains. The component *күңел* (“soul”), directly associated with the world of feelings as a source of emotions and a place of their accumulation, is often used in the phraseosemantic subgroup “Calmness, ease”: *күңел басылу – künel basyli; күңел булу – künel bulı; күңел бушау / бушау – künel bushau / bushatu; күңел даруы табу – künel darıy tabı; күңелгә җылы керү – künelgә zhyly kerü; күңелгә хуш килү – künelgә hush kilü; күңел кану / кандыру – künel kanı / kandyru.*

Another receptacle of emotion is the heart. The soul and heart can interact with a person’s emotional life and are often even interchangeable, as shown by the examples: *йөрәк басылу – jorak basyli; йөрәккә ял булу; йөрәк шатлану – jorakka yal bulı; йөрәк җырлау – jorak zhyrlau; йөрәк җанлан – jorak zhanlanı; йөрәк канатлану – jorak kanatlanı.* The lexeme *җан* (“soul”) is directly associated with the world of feelings: *җан керү – zhan kerü; җан рәхәте – zhan rabate; җан эрү – zhan eru; җан яну – zhan yanı; җан ташу – zhan tashı; җанга шифа булып яту – zhangа shifa bulyp yatu.*

In the phraseological units *җилкәдән тау төшү – zhilkadan tau toshı; җан тынычланым калу – zhan tynychlanıy kalı; җан тыну – zhan tını; күңел бушау – künel bushau; күңелдән таш төшү – küneldan tash toshı,* anxiety and difficulties are associated with a mountain of problems, hardships, and when a person gets rid of them, he or she attains calmness and joy. When a negative emotion, such as anger, subsides, a person finds peace: *ачу басылу – achı basyli; ачу бетү – achı betı; ачудан котылу – achıdan kotıly.* In the phraseosemantic subgroup “Calmness, ease”, the following components are used in phraseological units: *күңел, йөрәк – künel, jorak, җан – zhan.* After getting rid of negative emotions such as anxiety and anger, a person calms down, as evidenced by the examples.

Thus, language is the mirror of the people, reflecting its spirit, history, and the essence of life. One can turn to phraseological units to study any nation’s culture, mentality, customs, and worldview. The emotive component mainly determines the semantics of phraseological units. It is especially closely associated with the inner meaning of a phraseological unit. The internal form emerges employing a figurative representation of reality and carries motivation. It plays a significant role in determining its emotiveness. A phraseological unit does not lose its connotative component even with the loss of internal meaning, that is, unmotivated meaning.

4. Conclusion

Phraseological units that convey several related emotions can be united into phraseosemantic subgroups of surprise, grief, suffering, sadness, despondency, and joy and happiness (Husnutdinov, 2015), all of which are united into three main groups, namely, positive, negative, and neutral emotions. Two phraseosemantic subgroups denoting positive emotions were singled out as joy, happiness, calmness, and ease. Within each subgroup, phraseological units consist of components with national specificity. Active components of the phraseosemantic subgroup of “joy, happiness” are:

күк (“sky”): *күк капчысы ачылу – kuk kapısy achıly; бәхет ишеге ачылу – babet ishige achıly; җиде кат күккә менү – zhide kat kukka menı; җиденче кат күккә ашу – zhidenchı kat kukka ashı; түбәсе күккә тию / җитү – tubase kukka tiyu / zhitı; түбә түшәмгә очу – tuba tushamga ochı; башы күккә тию / күтәрелү – bashı kukka tiyu / kutareli; башы түбәгә тию – bashı tubaga tiyu;*

бәхет (“happiness”): *бәхет йөзлеге белән тии – babet jözlege belan tiı; бәхет йөзеге белән тии – babet jözge belan tiı*

Somatisms: *авыз калакка Жчиту; авыз еру; йөз яктыру / ачылы; эч катып көлү; аяк Жцирә тилмәү; йөз ачылы;*

йөрәк (“heart”), күңел (“soul”): *күңел күтәрелү – künel kütareli; күңел кинәнү – künel kinani; күңел кузгалу – künel kuzgali; күңел көрәю – künel koraui; йөрәк кабыну – jorak kabуни; йөрәк Жчилкенү – jorak çhilkeni; күңел канатлану – künel kanatlani, etc.*

Active components of the phraseosemantic subgroup calmness and ease are somatisms: *кул белән сытырын / сыйтан алгандай булу – kul belan суругур / сураф algandaj bulи, тел белән ялмап алгандай булу – tel belan yalmap algandaj bulи, карап белән юу – karash belan уни; карап белән ялмай – karash belan yalmai,*

күңел (“soul”): *күңел басылу – künel basуli; күңел булу – künel bulи; күңел бушау / бушату – künel bushau / bushatu; күңел даруы табу – künel darуy tabи; күңелгә Жчылы керү – künelgә Жчы керү; күңелгә хуш килү – künelgә hush kili; күңел кану / кандыру – künel kani / kandури; күңел көрәю – künel koraui; күңел тынычлан калу – künel тынчлар kali; күңел утыру – künel utури; күңел шакмак булу – künel shakmak bulи; күңел бөтен булу – künel boten bulи; күңел бөтәю – künel botauи; күңел килү – künel kili;*

йөрәк (“heart”): *йөрәк басылу – jorak basуli; йөрәккә ял булу – jorakka yal bulи; йөрәк шатлану – jorak shatlani; йөрәк Жырлау – jorak çhуrlau; йөрәк Жчанлану – jorak çhanlani; йөрәк канатлану – jorak kanatlani;*

Жсан (“soul”): *Жсан керү – çhan kerи; Жсан рәхәте – çhan rahate; Жсан эрү – çhan erу; Жсан яту – çhan yatu; Жсан ташу – çhan tashi; Жсанга шифа булып яту – çhanga shifa bulыp yatu; Жсанга яту – çhanga yatu;* words with the meaning of heaviness: *Жчилкәдән тау төшү – çhilkadan tau tesу; Жсан тынычланган калу – çhan тынчлануr kali; Жсан тыну – çhan тыни; күңел бушау – künel bushau; күңелдән таш төшү – küneldan tash tosу; ачу басылу – achi basуli; ачу бетү – achi betи; ачудан котылу – achudan kotуli, etc.*

In the phraseosemantic subgroup “calmness, ease”, the following components of phraseological units are used: *күңел, йөрәк – künel, jorak, Жсан – çhan.* A person calms down and becomes happy after getting rid of negative emotions, such as anxiety and anger. Hence, in Tatar linguistics, studying the ways of verbalization of emotionality by the example of Tatar phraseology makes it possible to present the possibilities of language and speech in a single complex and contributes to understanding the mentality and psychology of the Tatar linguistic personality. Thus, the relevance of this study is beyond dispute. Representations of the inner world create an emotional, conceptual framework in human consciousness. At first sight, emotion can be seen as universal since emotions are inherent in everyone. The expression of emotions is characteristic of any culture. People have always experienced the same emotions: joy, sadness, love, sorrow. However, language is not a mirror reflection of the world, so in different languages, the world of emotions and language units conveying them cannot wholly coincide with the representations of other people. Indeed, this does not mean one nation has emotions while another does not. Emotions are universal, but the typological structure of the emotional vocabulary of one language may not coincide with the emotional vocabulary of another language. Each language’s classification of emotions confirms the national and cultural specifics of emotional traits. Considering all these, it is necessary to develop exercises to master the most difficult-to-study verbs of motion from the semantics of close spheres. Perhaps it would be better to create dictionaries of such a verb.

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Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 22/03/2024).

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